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Case Study

Chronic Actinomycetoma of the Lower Limb Mimicking Other Infections—A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mycetoma is a long-term granulomatous condition that mostly affects the lower extremities. It shows up in the sinus tracts, granular pus discharge, and edema. It produces characteristic grains and is caused by either fungus (eumycetoma) or bacteria (actinomycetoma). It is characterized by swelling, sinus tract formation, and granular discharge, and may clinically mimic tuberculosis, osteomyelitis, or fungal infections, resulting in delayed diagnosis. Early differentiation between actinomycetoma and eumycetoma is essential because treatment strategies differ significantly. **Case Presentation:** A 32 year old Indian male presented with a two-year history of intermittent pain, swelling, and white granular discharge from a lesion on his left foot. Previous symptomatic treatments provided temporary relief without definitive diagnosis. Clinical examination showed localized swelling and purulent discharge, with stable vital signs and normal systemic findings. Gram staining demonstrated Actinomycetes, and histopathological examination confirmed actinomycetoma, while KOH preparation and culture were negative. The patient was treated with a modified two step regimen consisting of IV GENTAMICIN and oral TRIMETHOPRIM-SULFAMETHOXAZOLE during the intensive phase, followed by oral DOXYCYCLINE and TRIMETHOPRIM-SULFAMETHOXAZOLE in the maintenance phase. The patient showed significant improvement, including reduction in pain, swelling, and granular discharge, with no immediate complications. **Conclusion:** The uniqueness of this case lies in its occurrence in a less frequently reported region and confirmation of diagnosis despite negative culture findings. It gives the effectiveness of structured, prolonged antibiotic therapy without surgical intervention. Early recognition and appropriate management are crucial to prevent bone involvement, deformity, recurrence, and long-term disability...

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INTRODUCTION

Mycetoma is a granulomatous infection that is suppurative, progressive, and chronic; it mainly affects the skin, subcutaneous tissues, and underlying bones. It is common in tropical and subtropical areas and is frequently linked to the traumatic implantation of bacterial or fungal infections. The Atharva Veda, an ancient Sanskrit scripture from India, contains the first known mention of this illness. It talks of a malady called padavalmikam, which translates to "ANTHILL FOOT"[1]. More recently, in 1842, a researcher by the name of Gill discovered mycetoma as a separate illness in the southern Madura region. For this reason, the ailment gained widespread recognition as "Madura foot." In Madras, India, Godfrey was the first to record a mycetoma case. After learning that fungi are the source of the

illness, Carter later gave it the term "Mycetoma," which translates to "fungal tumor." [2]

Although mycetoma is present worldwide, it is most prevalent in tropical and subtropical climates, particularly in the "Mycetoma belt," which is the region between latitudes 15° S and 30° N. Sudan, Somalia, Senegal, India, Yemen, Mexico, Venezuela, Colombia, and Argentina are among these nations. But the illness is not limited to this area. Mexico and Sudan account for the majority of reported cases, with Sudan reporting the most cases. [3] Pinoy found in 1913 that there are two kinds of bacteria that produce mycetoma. He separated it into eumycetoma, which is caused by fungi, and actinomycetoma, which is caused by bacteria. [4]

The organisms responsible for mycetoma and the color of the grains they yield: [5]

Agent	Grain color
Actinomycotic	
<i>Nocardia asteroides</i>	White
<i>Nocardia brasiliensis</i>	White
<i>Nocardia otitidiscaviarum</i>	White
<i>Actinomadura madurae</i>	White
<i>Actinomadura pelletieri</i>	Red to pink
<i>Streptomyces somaliensis</i>	White to yellow
Eumycotic	
<i>Madurella mycetomatis</i>	Black to brown
<i>Madurella grisea</i>	Black to brown
<i>Leptosphaeria senegalensis</i>	Black
<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	Black
<i>Neotestidina rosatii</i>	Yellow
<i>Acremonium</i> spp.	White to yellow
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	White to pale yellow
<i>Scedosporium apiospermum</i>	White to pale yellow

Clinical Features of Actinomycetoma and Eumycetoma and Characteristics of the Principal [6]

	Actinomycetoma	Eumycetoma
Pathogen	Bacteria	Fungi
Pathogenesis	Fast	Slow
Gross Appearance	Grain discharge, numerous sinuses, and diffuse lesions without a distinct border	One or more nodules with a distinct border and a few or few sinuses
Body Region involved	60% of mycetoma's are found in the foot, with the trunk(chest and back),arms, forearms, legs, knees,	Mycetoma primarily affects the foot (70%) and hand (10%), with

	thighs, hands, shoulders, and abdominal wall following.	the remaining 20% occurring in various body areas.
Lesion	The diffuse margins are unclear. More inflammatory More damaging	Capably summarized, Margin of clarity, Decreased inflammation Not as damaging

Summary of diagnostic investigations [5]

Method	Salient points	
	Advantages	Disadvantage
Direct microscopy	Simple outpatient procedure Quick diagnosis of causative organism and hence classification as eumycetoma or actinomycetoma	
Histology	In case of eumycetoma, suppurative granulomas composed of neutrophils are seen surrounding characteristic grains Actinomycetoma histopathology shows the homogeneous eosinophilic material around the grain in a star-shaped manner (Splendore-Hoeppli reaction)	Expertise required is not available at most places
Culture	Species-specific diagnosis is possible	Readily not available Long growth time
Serology	Detection of circulating antibodies Good sensitivity for detection of cases early in the course	Readily not available Costly
Radiology	Reveal bony involvement such as periosteal erosion secondary to invasion, osteoporosis, lytic cavities, and changes consistent with osteomyelitis	
Ultrasonography	Differentiates the mycetoma from osteomyelitis or tumor Eumycetoma produces single or multiple thick-walled cavities, without acoustic enhancement. In actinomycetoma, the grains produce fine echoes that are usually found at the bottom of the cavities	
CT	Good sensitivity for early detection of bone involvement	
MRI	Most comprehensive method for assessment of the bone and soft tissue involvement A dot-in-circle sign has been described as a potentially specific diagnostic finding seen with MRI	

CT: Computerized tomography, MRI: Magnetic resonance imaging

Antibiotics are typically effective in treating actinomycetomas. The infection has been well treated with medications such as AMOXICILLIN-CLAVULANIC ACID, TRIMETHOPRIM, STREPTOMYCIN, DAPSONE, COTRIMOXAZOLE, AND RIFAMPICIN. [7]

Treatment for Actinomycetoma. [8] Modified two-step regimen [2007]

1. Intensive Phase

Gentamicin (80 mg twice daily, IV), and cotrimoxazole (two tablets of 960 mg twice daily) for 4 weeks.

2. Maintenance Phase

Doxycycline (100 mg orally, twice daily), and cotrimoxazole (two tablets of 960 mg twice daily), until 5–6 months after complete healing of all sinuses.

CASE REPORT: -

A 32-year-old Indian male presented with a complaint of a skin lesion once left foot over the previous 2 years. Pain occurs once a lesion is

intermittent in nature and increases in doing work and touch, particularly relieved on medication. There was presence of white-colored grain discharge from their lesion along with swelling of the left foot which was not relieved on taking medication. In past, 2 or 3 times the patient visited a primary care hospital with the same complaint but upon taking the medication, it got relieved.

Upon examination, the patient exhibited vital signs within normal limits: pulse rate of 78 beats per minute, respiratory rate of 18 breaths per minute, and blood pressure of 130/80 mmHg. Systemic evaluations including cardiovascular, central nervous system, endocrine, and gastrointestinal assessments were all normal. Locally, the examination revealed a shine-coloured, swelling, and pus discharge in the left foot.

Laboratory tests indicated normal complete blood count and liver function with alkaline phosphate recorded at 172 U/L. Renal function tests yield a serum creatinine level of 1.22 mg/dl. Random blood glucose measurement was 122 mg/dl.

Diagnostic test: -

- Gram Stain - Actinomycetes Positive
- Biopsy - Actinomycetoma Positive
- KOH preparation - Negative
- Culture and sensitivity - Negative

These reports gave a positive diagnosis of Actinomycetes of the patient, who was not having any previous history of such kind of signs and symptoms.

Treatment Given as per the modified 2-step regimen (2007): - (intensive phase)

- INJ. GENTAMICIN, 80 mg, IV, 12 hourly (28 days)
- TAB. TRIMETHOPRIM + SULFAMETHOXAZOLE, 960 mg, PO, 2-0-2 (28 days)

Discharge medication:

Drug name	Dose	Route	Duration
CAP. DOXYCYCLINE	100 mg	PO	1-0-1(30 days)
TAB. TRIMETHOPRIM + SULFAMETHOXAZOLE	960 mg	PO	2-0-2 (30 days)
TAB. PANTOPRAZOLE	40 mg	PO	1-0-1 (30 days)
TAB. MVBC		PO	1-0-1 (30 days)
TAB. FOLIC ACID	5 mg	PO	0-1-0 (30 days)

DISCUSSION

In 1842, mycetoma was discovered for the first time in Tamil Nadu, India's Madurai area. When it was discovered there, it was called "Madura Foot." Usually beginning in the foot, it is a chronic infection that affects the skin, muscles, and bones. Certain bacteria or fungi are the source of the illness, which can result in deformities, swelling, and pus-filled sores. It has the potential to spread and cause serious harm if untreated. [9] Three primary symptoms of mycetoma, a persistent infection, are swelling of the affected area, numerous lesions that drain pus, and the presence of minute grains (granules) in the discharge. Actinomycetoma (also known as actinomycotic mycetoma) is caused by bacteria belonging to the Actinomycetes group, while eumycetoma is caused by fungus. Typically, the illness affects the hands, legs, and feet; if treatment is not received, the tissues will eventually enlarge and deteriorate. [10]

In the case study, a 32-year-old man from Gujarat has a chronic lesion on his left foot that has been causing him to have periodic discomfort, swelling,

and white granular discharge for the past two years. The symptoms persisted even after several trips to the primary care physician. Gram stain (Actinomycetes seen) and biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of actinomycetoma, but KOH preparation and culture were negative, ruling out eumycetoma. Osteomyelitis, TB, and persistent bacterial infections were among the differential diagnoses, highlighting the importance of microbiological confirmation. An intensive phase of IV gentamicin and oral trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole was administered for 28 days as part of a modified two-step treatment regimen. This was followed by a maintenance phase that included oral doxycycline, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, pantoprazole, folic acid, and MVBC for 30 days. After 30 days, a follow-up appointment was set up for the patient to evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment and, if need, modify it. Upon examination the patient showed improved signs and symptoms. Photos of the patient responding to the therapy is also provided. Picture 1: Patient showing improved signs and symptoms with less pain. The pus-filled areas were

treated and the pus has disappeared leaving behind dark-colored pigmented patches as shown below:

Since mycetoma is frequently misdiagnosed due to delayed presentation, which can result in consequences including bone involvement, this example emphasizes the significance of early detection. Considering that it is endemic in tropical areas like India, raising awareness and making sure that long-term antibiotic therapy is followed are essential for minimizing disability and enhancing patient outcomes.

According to Talwar et al., [11] 70% of individuals with actinomycotic mycetoma had foot involvement. Although this illness can strike anyone at any age or location in the world, middle-aged adults are most likely to get it. It is three times more common in men than in women. [12]

For physicians, treating mycetoma is extremely difficult. To stop the infection and avoid antibiotic resistance, the treatment typically consists of a combination of medications. In this instance, the patient received five weeks of Rifampicin, Bactrim DS, and Dapsone. The course of treatment was extended for six months since the patient showed improvement, including less discomfort and swelling. Mycetoma is an uncommon occurrence in Central India, which is what makes this instance unique.

Limitation of the study:-

Limitations include Negative culture results, and lack of long-term follow-up to assess recurrence.

CONCLUSION

There are very few known occurrences of mycetoma in Central India, which is why this case is being reported. It draws attention to the necessity of raising awareness among physicians and microbiologists to enable prompt diagnosis and treatment. Patient care can be improved by early diagnosis and timely treatment, which can also help predict the prognosis of such instances and reduce serious sequelae.

Abbreviations

- KOH – Potassium Hydroxide
- TB – Tuberculosis
- MVBC – Multivitamins B Complex
- TAB - Tablet
- CAP - Capsule
- INJ - Injection
- IV- Intravenous
- Mg - Milligram

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